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Research Article

**RISING TRENDS OF BLOOD DONATION AND
TRANSFUSION IN PAKISTANI POPULATION**¹Dr. Sidra Choaudhary, ²Dr. Fatima Altaf, ³Dr. Hassan Iftikhar¹WMO Tehsil Head Quarter Ahmad Pur Sial²Services Hospital Lahore³DHQ Hospital Kasur**Abstract:**

Objectives: Giving blood to help others and transfer of donated blood to other human being are safe methods. But awareness, faiths and stances are linked with these two medical terms and can affect the safety of procedures. The main idea of this research was to describe the awareness faiths and stances about giving and transferring of blood in the people of Pakistan.

Methodology: This research was held at Mayo Hospital Lahore, Pakistan. Questions were prepared to check the faiths, behaviour and awareness for giving and transferring of blood in population.

Results: Three hundred and thirty-five men and two hundred and seventy-four women were the participants of this study. More than sixty-five percent participants never donated blood. About eighty percent on non-donors were from fifteen years to thirty year of age. There was a belief in more eighty-eight percent participants that donation of the blood to the human being is not an unhealthy activity. Twenty percent participants had the view that they would reject the transferring of the blood or plasma if they were in a condition of danger because it would bring complicated diseases to them from other persons. There were some participants who believed that they would receive blood only from their relatives. They were forty-nine percent.

Conclusion: The mistaken belief about the donation of the blood and its transfusion should be tackled by the education, ending up the false ideas about the hospitals and ignorance. This will motivate the donors to perform the noble deed. People should be awaked that several preventive measures are taken to handle the donation of blood and transferring of blood in the recipient.

Keywords: faith, ignorance, behaviour, stance, donor, recipient, transfusion, donation.

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INTRODUCTION:

Different research proved fail in searching out a complete in lieu of the blood and its main components as RBC, WBC, serum and platelets etc. So, for the completion of the need of blood components and blood, the donation of the blood will continue forever by human beings. There are many occasions in which persons can loss their large amount of blood such as wars between countries, during surgeries, in serious accidents and there are some diseases which directly involve the blood as anaemia in which red blood cells are in low quantity and an individual feels tired or low platelet quantity in the blood [1]. So, blood donation is a very noble act and saver of the human life. It is the responsibility of the blood stores to give the proper blood group and clear supply to the populations. The ratio between donors and recipients always fluctuates and does not remain on equilibrium condition. There are several types of donation as on payment donation, willing donation and direct donation [2]. These donations are the way of getting the blood and its important ingredients. The willing donors should be examined carefully before obtaining blood. Direct donors are the relative or close family friends from whom blood is transferred to specific recipient. On payment donation is carried out by exchange of cash. In autologous donation, the donor and the recipient is the same person. Blood is stored in safe condition and then transfused to same person at the time of surgery [3]. Ignorance faiths and the stances are the things which can motivate or depress the donors of blood.

The process of transferring blood and its ingredients varies from department to department. This process depends upon the service provided by the LAB and quantity of the sufferers available [4]. According to the need of the recipients' blood plasma or blood ingredients are transfused to the sufferers. It is common belief that transfusion of

blood is a dangerous act, although many preventive steps have been taken in the same field to prevent the infections. This research provides us with the faith and knowledge of community about donation of blood and transfer of blood from one person to another. The outcome of this study will end up the misconception arising about blood transfusion and blood donation [5].

METHODOLOGY:

This research was carried out in Mayo Hospital Lahore, Pakistan from 2015 to 2016. Good ordered questions were used to check the faith, ideas, behaviour, stances and awareness about the processes of blood transfer from one person to another person and donation of blood in six hundred and nine participants of Pakistan. The social and economical data was gathered by question answer session. Three hundred and thirty five males and two hundred and seventy four females from fifteen years to sixty five years of age were the participants of this research. This age is the prerequisite for the donation of blood. The purpose of study was introduced to the participants. Social science version twelve SSV12 was used for data entry.

RESULTS:

The outcome was collected from six hundred and nine participants. In this research, fifty five percent were males and forty five percent were the female participants. Sixty five point eighty four percent participants were not donors. The non blood donors gave some reasons of not donating blood as they were never asked to donate blood, ignorance, long distance from place of donation, time management, misconception and difficulty in transportation. Table number one gives the division of two group i.e. donors of blood and non-donor of blood, a large quantity of the participants was from fifteen to thirty years of age.

Table-I: Distribution of sample into donors and non-donors according to age

Age group	Donors	Non-donors	Total
15-30 years	153	328	481
30-45 years	42	59	101
45-60 years	11	7	18
More than 60 years	2	7	9

Table-II: Distribution of sample into donors and non-donors according to gender

Gender	Donors	Non-donors	Total
Male	185	150	335
Female	23	251	274

Table-III: Attitude, beliefs and level of knowledge regarding blood donation and blood transfusion.

Question	Males		Females	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
Is blood donation harmful to the donor?	28	307	42	232
Have you ever needed blood transfusion?	14	321	24	250
Will you accept blood transfusion if you are in need?	52	283	70	204
Do you prefer to know the donor or not?	266	69	249	25
Are you going to accept blood donation only from a relative?	125	210	174	100
Did you or a family member acquire any disease after transfusion?	28	307	43	231
Do you think that the blood in the blood bank is safe?	220	115	116	158
Does all surgical procedure require blood transfusion?	72	263	34	240

Table-IV: Gender preference for donation

Gender	Male donors	Female Donors	Male or Female	Total
Male	217	38	80	335
Female	66	159	49	274
Total	283	197	129	609

Table-V: Level of knowledge regarding blood supply level at blood banks

Question	Males			Females		
	Lees than needed	More than needed	Do not know	Lees than needed	More than needed	Do not know
What is your idea about the available blood supply in the blood banks?	120	10	208	53	03	215

The large quantity of the non-donors were women and seventy-five-point ninety six percent donors of blood were men. Table no 2 shows that both groups are well qualified. Table no 3 provides about the ideas, faiths, behaviours and awareness about donation and transferring of blood. Eighty eight point five percent participants viewed that donation of blood is not a dangerous activity because preventive tests are carried out before start of donation of blood. Eleven point five percent (majority were females) viewed that the donation of blood can cause any disease infection. More than six percent participants received blood one time in their lives. Twenty percent refused from blood transfusion even if they would be in danger and in need of blood because it would lead to the infection. Eighty four point five percent participants gave their votes in favour of donation from direct donors. This would end up every risk of getting any disease. Forty nine percent would get transfusion of blood from only close relatives. Fifty five point one percent samples were in favour of the storage and transfusion of blood from blood banks and other forty four point five were against this. Process of transfusion of the blood caused

AIDS and hepatitis in their close relation mentioned by eleven point six percent samples.

Table - 4 provides the data of sex preference for receiving donation of blood. Most of the samples preferred to receive blood from females because in the population of Pakistan, females have fewer chances to get infected by any infectious disease than men. The blood was required or not required by the blood banks; sixty nine point five percent samples do not know this. This data is provided in table no 5.

DISCUSSION:

The health planners of Pakistan are trying to maintain safe and secure procedure for the supply of the blood. This issue cannot be underestimated due to large amount of increased population and increase in the demand of blood. So, it is very important to interpret the ideas, behaviours, awareness and faiths of the people which are linked with the process of donation of blood and transfusion of blood from one person to another.

A large quantity of samples of this study was non donors. The non blood donors gave some reasons of not donating blood as they were never asked to

donate blood, ignorance, long distance from place of donation, time management, misconception and difficulty in transportation. The studies done in the past also provides the same causes of not donating the blood. Thomson reported that eighty percent of the blood donors who are donating their blood for the very first time would never come back. Misconceptions, different doubts and ignorance are the different main hindrances in inhibiting donating blood. To wash out these types of fallacies from the minds of the people, seminars and different programs should be introduced.

Discrimination due to different race, age and sex are some other factors of inhibiting donation. In this research, males' percentage of donors was greater than females' donors. Most of the non donors were from fifteen to thirty years of age. So, motivation and education can kill this factor. It is the duty of blood centres to make sure that it will not jeopardize the life of the donor. In this research, eleven point five percent samples believe that it is a dangerous activity. Sharma provided the same opinion in his four percent participants. AIDS and hepatitis are the result of the blood donation in France as provided by Munoz.

Eighty four point five percent samples of this research work gave their vote in favour of direct donors because it would terminate the danger of getting any dangerous infection. Forty nine percent samples viewed that they would receive blood only from close relatives. According to a research [7], autologous donation is the best option to mitigate the concept of the infections. Twenty percent samples were against the transfusion in every condition because of fear of getting any dangerous complication. Eleven point six percent samples gave data about their close relation who got AIDS and hepatitis from transfusion. Love discovered that a single donor of hepatitis c infected blood transfusion can affect a large number of the recipients.

Media programs and internet should be used for the awareness of the population about the processes of blood transfusion and blood donations [8]. Such programs would encourage and motivate the persons to donate blood. It would ensure the availability of blood for every patient. The populations should get awareness that the different types of the preventive tests carried out by the blood centre are the ways ensuring safety for both blood donors and blood recipients.

CONCLUSION:

The mistaken belief about the donation of the blood and its transfusion should be tackled by the education, ending up the false ideas about the hospitals and ignorance. This will motivate the

donors to perform the noble deed. People should be awaked that several preventive measures are taken to handle the donation of blood and transferring of blood in the recipient.

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